

The brave new chemist : challenges for 21st century[†]

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The problems facing chemical education in India and the consequent challenges to the chemists are briefly discussed.

A cynical question often posed by the new generation is who in his/her right mind would choose to pursue a career in Chemistry today? But let us be honest here. If the Fellows of the Indian Chemical Society were 18 again and planning a career, would chemistry be their first choice? In most cases, the answer is No. Can we then really blame young people for choosing another career? What kind of future can chemistry graduates expect these days? Many of the chemistry graduates are welcomed in professions like accountancy or banking where their analytical skills come in useful, and the financial rewards are substantial. One will find the chemists working in all sorts of diverse professions today. They are working in the chemical and pharmaceutical industry, in agriculture and food industry, in paper, rubber and plastic production, in metallurgy and construction materials, energy production, in mechanical, electronics, aerospace industries and even in hotels, commerce, transport and administration. In a lighter vein, more than a decade back, nearly a dozen chemistry professors were serving as Vice-chancellors in various Indian Universities.

Till about two decades ago, a career in Chemistry seemed pretty good. Whether one went into industry or academics, one would expect a challenging career with a reasonable status and respect in society. It was also a profession which was perceived by those outside it as respectable. Not so any more. Chemists now rank alongside the more traditional "social lepers" and this factor is undoubtedly as much a consideration in career choice as factors such as pay.

Challenges of Chemistry

The 20th century saw great advances in the sciences and technology. The rapid and fruitful development of scientific research and teaching at universities laid the foundation of establishment of various industries whose processes were based on the scientific achievements of the learned scientists and engineers. In fact, when after independence, various

National Laboratories and Research Institutions were established by the Government of India, most of the research staff in senior positions was drafted from the Indian Universities. The Chemistry Departments of most of the Indian Universities around 1947 had established good reputation in spite of meagre resources. In most cases, the faculty had eminent persons as Chairmen of the University Departments in various science subjects. I (KCJ) recall that in my own *alma mater*, Lucknow University, Professor Mc Mahon, one of the founders of the Indian Science Congress Association, was the Chairman of the Department. Soon, the country faced the colossal problem of educating millions of students at all levels and in all disciplines and there was a tremendous increase in the number of institutions of higher learning and students enrolled (Till 1998, there were nearly 240 Universities, 8613 colleges, 61.13 lakh students and 2.87 lakh teachers). And yet, the financial allocations to the Central and State Universities have been correspondingly decreasing. In India, funding from other sources like industry and private endowments are practically nil. This has resulted in a resource-crunch and deterioration in academic standards. Besides, inspiring teachers are rare and in fact, it is a vanishing tribe! The academic scenario in our institutions has deteriorated to such an extent that some years ago, the prestigious journal, *Nature*¹, observed :

".....The Indian University system is certainly the largest in the world and probably also the most chaotic. Some institutions are good. Most are afflicted by a host of problems-inadequate students, too many students, too much external political influence, academic nepotism (or even corruption), exclusive concern for academic qualification and status, meaningless or even phoney research. The wonder is merely that so many young people survive the system even wresting an education from it..."

While this deterioration has pervaded all scientific disciplines, it is more than true for Chemistry. This is because

[†]This article is dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji in view of his abiding interest in Chemical Education.

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during the past fifty years, chemistry has made major advances on two fronts. The first is in chemical knowledge itself and in the Chemists' ability to understand, predict and control chemical phenomena. A mere look at the increasing size and cost of *Chemical Abstracts* is enough to convince one of this explosion. Millions of chemical compounds are already reported and about fifty thousand compounds are in use. It took about 32 years to make the first million entries in the *Chemical Abstracts* but now one million publications are reported in less than two years. Yet it will be interesting to find out that in this age of explosion in Information Technology, how many of our departments of chemistry have access to *Chemical Abstracts* and other International Journals. This advancement in chemistry has been made possible mainly by the development of sophisticated instrumentation and a powerful, pervasive structural theory. The second major advancement involves the far-reaching applications of chemical principles and specially structural theory in biology, medicine, nutrition, geology, astronomy, engineering sciences and in nearly every area of technology. It is not necessary that most of the persons responsible for applying chemistry may themselves be chemists but they must have been influenced by their chemistry teachers. The spectacular success of the Human Genome Project is a good example of this.

Challenges of the individual

The factors cited above have created a situation in which constant improvement and innovation in methods of chemical education are needed. As chemistry continues its rapid development and in fact becomes an influential component of our culture, chemistry teachers must find new and more effective ways of keeping themselves upto date in the subject.

Although the chemistry teachers' job is interesting, it is now more challenging than ever. In chemical education, "a teacher who doesn't learn something new in chemistry or about teaching every month cannot continue to be effective". Perhaps, the most basic of all teaching methods for chemistry was described by H. F. Davison² in 1926 as follows :

"Chemistry is a study of matter and it can never be adequately learned from books. Students must see the material that is talked about and must eventually handle it themselves. But beginners have to be shown what chemicals will do and how they are best handled. This is the business of the teacher...".

The rising scientific level of the chemical sciences puts high demand for abstract reasoning in students and the number of students with high level of intelligence is

increasing rapidly. This situation needs teachers of excellence and thus efforts should be made and conditions created where really brilliant chemists remain in the teaching profession. Alas, it is not so at present. Our political masters donot seem to have a need for professional excellence. A recent issue of the widely read magazine, "*Outlook*", had described in detail the callousness of the various State Governments in funding the Universities and recruiting qualified teachers³.

For an individual teacher, chemistry is not mere knowledge of facts and theories. In a situation where knowledge is rapidly becoming obsolete, it is equally important that the method of acquiring and validating fresh knowledge should be encouraged. Our society is getting transformed from a traditional to a more modern society. Therefore a chemistry teacher is expected to take advantage of recent developments in educational technology – the audio and visual components, the opportunities of self-learning and distance education and the immense possibility of computers.

The evolution of a good chemist is maximum during the age span of 20–40. This needs a "Continuing Professional Development" (CPD). The continuing professional development can take many forms – both formal and informal. Open Learning provides flexible opportunities which meet the specific needs of a chemist in terms of content, time, place and pace of study.

This results in life-long education, and trains the employees to adapt quickly to meet the demands of a new job. As mentioned above, CPD can take many forms as depicted below :

Fig. 1. Continuing professional development⁴.

Teaching chemistry through distance education

Nearly three decades after the first correspondence courses were introduced by the University of Delhi, the concept of distance education is now well recognised in India as a viable mode of education. After independence, India faced the colossal problem of educating millions of students at all levels and in all disciplines. The Planning Commission of the Government of India appointed an expert committee under the chairmanship of the eminent

educationist. Dr. D. S. Kothari⁵ to examine the possibility of starting correspondence courses in a few select Universities of India. The commission noted that since independence, there has been a tremendous increase in the number of institutions of higher learning and students enrolled.

The Indian Education Commission (1964-66) discussed all these factors and observed that, "there must also be a method of taking education to the millions who depend upon their own efforts to study courses and provide right answer for these situations". This will ensure that education can be made accessible to all and further, life-long education will be available for all stages of life.

As mentioned earlier, the teaching of chemistry poses challenges in more than one way⁶. It is offered by the largest number of students opting for the science stream. However, for a great majority of students, chemistry as a subject is of only terminal interest. Therefore, the needs of such chemists cannot be adequately tackled by a non-flexible conventional class-room system. Open-learning programme is targeted at a heterogeneous group comprising persons such as school teachers, laboratory technicians, small scale entrepreneurs, house wives, fresh 10 + 2 pass outs, people living in geographically remote and educationally backwards areas etc. Therefore, the concept of distance education keeps participants in getting adequate training in chemistry which otherwise is denied to them and improve their job promotion chances. Thus, innovative approaches like non-formal education, correspondence courses, open university, open school, off-campus courses etc. have been implemented and popularised both in developing and developed countries. This also ensures life-long education and this is accessible to all irrespective of financial, social and psychological conditions.

The School of Correspondence Course and Continuing Education of the University of Delhi was the first to start B.Sc. courses in the country in 1969. The next serious effort to teach chemistry was made in 1983 by Dr. B. R. Ambedkar Open University, Hyderabad. However, a major effort at the national level was made by the establishment of the Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU) as an apex Open University in 1985. IGNOU has been offering Chemistry courses at the B.Sc. level since 1992. In this, the University had the advantage of being familiar with the excellent courses in chemistry prepared by the British Open University at Milton Keynes. The latter has devised a syllabus which strikes a balance between the traditional ways of dividing up chemistry for teaching purposes and the more radical emphasis on only theoretical and general chemistry.

The IGNOU follows a modular and flexible approach based on credit system. By and large IGNOU and UKOU follow the same flexibility and openness but there can be a difference in the extent. A major consideration in curriculum design at IGNOU has been to ensure parity with the undergraduate programmes in the conventional Indian Universities. This programme⁷ is offered in English as well as in Hindi through a networks of 21 Regional Centres and 75 Study Centres spread throughout the country.

After success of the IGNOU programme, which is an apex body in the country for open learning, most of the major states of India are establishing their own Open Universities at the state level and this is bound to give an impetus to not only students learning chemistry but also to established chemists to improve their professional efficiency.

Problems of curriculum development

In most of the western countries, chemistry courses were drastically changed during 1960's. There was a transition from descriptive type of chemistry to theoretical and general chemistry. Quite often, the change was too drastic. In January 1988 issue of "*Chemistry in Britain*", an interesting article appeared on 'Recruitment of Chemists' which narrated the experience of interviewing 'Oxbridge' graduates who could not write the formula for phenol and did not know if barium sulphate was a solid or a gas. It was then realized that a logical and rational development between theory and experiment should be retained. Curriculum development involves a broad concept which includes the rapid expansion of the subject, its diversification, the needs of the society as well as development of human resources for different national tasks. Therefore, any exercise in curriculum development should be able to plan, devise and implement a course of study taking into account the variations in student background, skills and needs. In India, due to the vastness of the country, there is a great variation in the calibre of students and quality of teaching from place to place. There are some very brilliant students but they are engulfed in a quagmire of mediocrity. The net result is these students have to pass through the same grind and there is no flexibility. The American Semester System could have been an ideal way for catering to the needs of this variation in the quality of the students – with its tremendous flexibility and variety of alternate courses but unfortunately, the so-called semester system in India has failed. The main reason is that those who matter in the University Administration, have no idea of the American Semester System. They have treated it as the old half-yearly examination. The philosophy behind the genuine semester system is completely different which is not understood in India.

Some years back, the University Grants Commission established Curriculum Development Centres (CDCs) in the country in various disciplines for framing syllabi considering the needs of the country. The senior author (KCJ) had the privilege of being the coordinator of the CDC in chemistry at Jaipur and a comprehensive report was submitted to the UGC in June 1988. The CDC included eminent University and college teachers, representatives from industries, commercial organisations, government departments and research institutions. It was an extensive exercise and the CDC prepared a 'model syllabus' with considerable flexibility. A major recommendation was that chemistry teaching has to be integrated with related scientific discipline. No chemist can work in isolation these days. It is gratifying to note that a number of institutions have taken advantage of this report.

In the end, we would like to recall the words of a leading chemical educator, Professor Aleksandra Kornhauser, the then Director of International Centre for Chemical Studies, Ljubljana, former Yugoslavia :

".....Next to the needs of society and the growing field of chemistry, chemistry teaching has also to cope with the problems of the individual. Chemistry is not easy to learn and consequently not easy to teach. The "alphabet of chemis-

try", i.e. the minimum "critical knowledge" of facts and theories needed for basic understanding of this discipline is extensive. Abstract concepts and the use of mathematics make it more demanding to study. Another pre-requisite is the precise work expected in the laboratory. The enrolment in chemistry is often low and even some chemists think that we could and should not do anything about this phenomenon forgetting that chemistry is really necessary if we are to solve society's problems.....".

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